

IMPROVING SCIENTIFIC CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article examines the problems of improving the creative and scientific activity of the future primary school teacher. It was analyzed based on these data. Also, in the article, the formative method for improving the creative and scientific activity of future elementary school teachers, as well as the analysis of the fundamental views and theories of scientists, were considered. The author commented on the concept of creative approach and analyzed this topic from a pedagogical and psychological point of view. The level of the article is determined by the fact that the research works of foreign and local scientists on this topic are covered.*

Keywords: *creativity, approach, category, pedagogical research, intellectual talent, creativity, primary education, children's literature, competence, folk art, teacher, student, education, education, aesthetic pleasure, speech, literacy, pedagogy, theory.*

Introduction. In the reform of national education in our republic, on the basis of the principles of national independence based on national and universal value, the rich intellectual heritage of our people, the development of spiritual and moral qualities of future teachers at all stages of education, as well as the training of future teachers. The content of the development of measures to strengthen the role of public organizations, neighborhoods, local and international funds in spiritual, moral, intellectual and physical education is being further improved.[1]

The individual trajectory of the independent educational activity of each teacher, who is a participant in the formative experience of improving the creative and scientific activity of future elementary school teachers, is based on self-knowledge, creative activity. It is organized from the starting point where the work of determining the need is carried out, to the level of self-organization for creative activity and creative formation. From a psychological point of view, there is no significant difference between the creative activity of a scientist who discovers objective new laws of the surrounding world that are not yet known to mankind, and the productive thinking of a teacher who discovers new things only for himself, because these are based on psychic laws. Therefore, in the experiment, the forms, methods and means of independent educational activities of future elementary school teachers are chosen similar to those available for future elementary school teachers. However, just as the level of mental activity that leads to discovery is different, the conditions for finding new knowledge are also different. In order to identify such differences, most researchers prefer to call similar activities of schoolchildren by the term "productive activity", and the term "creative activity" is used to discover something completely new and unique to human knowledge. They use it to understand the highest level of the thinking activity of those who do it.

Analysis of literature on the topic. One of the most favorable young periods for the development of creative activity, V.N. According to Druzhin, this is the age of a junior school. At this young age, in primary education, students' mental abilities, imagination, thinking, and attention develop, and the ability to creative activity develops. A number of psychologists and pedagogues: A.V. Petrovsky, B.M. Teplov, V.A. According to Krutetsky, E. Ghaziyev, G.

Shoumarov, O. Rozikov, B. Adizov, - during this period, under the influence of educational activities, children's mental activity, attention, memory, level of perception, thinking, feeling 'usi-like processes develop.

Uzbek psychologists about the psychology of the junior high school youth period, its psychological characteristics, including E. Ghaziyev (youth period, worldview, faith, point of view, position, self-awareness), M. Davletshin (creative thinking psychodiagnostics), Z. Nishonova (students' mental qualities and factors affecting them), F. Akramova's scientific researches and theoretical views about the social causes of the violation of discipline among students, the sensitive period for the formation of personal qualities served during the lesson. From foreign scientists L.S. About the cultural-historical principle of Vygotsky's study of the psyche; D.A. Leontev about active approach; A.V. Petrovsky, B.M. Teplov, V.A. Krutetsky, E. Ghaziyev, G. Shoumarov, O. Rozikov, B. Adizov about primary school students; A. M. Matyushkin, I. S. Averina, G. D. Chistyakova on issues of organizing the creative activity of a student; N. Kh. Yunusova about the problem of educating primary school age students with the help of creative activities; Gilford, Torrens, Gettsels and Jackson, Bogoyavlenskaya, Druzhinin, Kholodnaya's scientific views on creativity. Many studies have been conducted by scientists from foreign countries and our republic on the problem of creating and using modern didactic teaching tools in the training of primary education teachers. In particular, on improving the methodology of teaching mathematics in primary classes: in our Republic, B. Abdullaeva, K. Kasimova, R.A. Mavlonova, N.U. Bikbayeva, M. Ahmedov, N. Abdurakhmonova, R. Ibragimov, in foreign countries: L.S.H. Levenberg, M.I. Mopo, A.M. Pishkalo, L.S.H. Levenberg, Y.M. Kolyagin, P.M. The research works of scientists like Erdniyev were systematically implemented in the preparation of this research work.

Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent. According to the American psychologist P. Torrens, "creativity is a problem or putting forward scientific hypotheses; hypothesis testing and modification; identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results; expresses sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem" [4].

Competence is the Latin word "Competentia", the dictionary meaning of which in Uzbek means "a person who knows well", "has experience". Competence is the ability to do a job effectively, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of work, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of specific work functions. [5]

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. L.M. Mitina pedagogical competence means knowledge about the subject, teaching methodology and didactics, pedagogical communication skills and competence, as well as self-development, self-improvement, self-realization understood the harmonious combination of methods and means of improvement. He distinguished the following three constituents in the structure of pedagogical competence: active, communicative and personal. Based on the structuring of pedagogical competence proposed by L.M. Mitina, we believe that the following set of competences, which determine the level of development of pedagogical competence for future specialists, are sufficient and necessary: - active or special competence (knowledge, skills, competence and pedagogical individual methods of activity implementation); - personal or professional competence

(knowledge, skills and abilities related to professional self-improvement and self-realization); - communicative competence (knowledge, skills and competence related to the creative implementation of pedagogical activity) Concepts of professionalism and competence have common features. [5]

Research methodology. Improving the creative activity of future elementary school teachers requires the inclusion of creative tasks, non-standard situations and their corresponding forms, methods and tools in independent educational activities. Professional creative needs and motivation play an important role in improving the creative activity of future primary school teachers. As a result of the formation of the creative activity of future elementary school teachers and their work on themselves, professional competence begins to appear. [2]

Nature of creative activity; the direct participation of teachers in the selection of non-standard tasks, the use of significant situations for the person in which the value-motivational, constructive and reflexive-objective components of the creative activity of future elementary school teachers are updated are the determining factors for improving the creative activity of elementary school teachers.

Let's take a closer look at the diagnostic stage of the technology for improving the creative activity of future primary school teachers.

At the diagnostic stage, the psychologist of the educational institution works with the teachers who expressed a desire to participate in the workshop (experimental group) and volunteer teachers of primary schools (control group) and they have the creative work of the future primary school teacher determines the initial level of development of competence and the existing conditions for its development. Diagnosis allows establishing compliance of the studied phenomenon with certain norms and criteria. In the process of diagnosing and evaluating the level of development of the initial creative competence of future primary school teachers, the pedagogical conditions necessary for optimizing the process of improving the creative activity of future primary school teachers are identified and clarified; the characteristics of the development of creative activity and some of its psychological and pedagogical mechanisms are studied. In particular, the diagnostic data obtained at this stage serve as "input" data for the next design stage. [6]

The purpose of the diagnostic stage is to develop the need to improve the creative activity of future elementary school teachers. At this stage, the experience is replicated to analyze the experience and share it with colleagues. At this stage, priority is given to partial search methods, which include partial explanation of new ideas by setting problems; problematic situations are created in the educational work of the participants of the workshop. A skilled teacher guides and corrects the work of colleagues using search methods, encourages workshop participants to conduct individual research, conduct research, and work independently with scientific literature, reference books, tables, and the Internet. The method serves as a way to carefully understand the qualitative actions of a person, to develop the ability to choose, reflexivity, functions, and to organize the process of creative interaction. Search methods occupy a worthy place in creative activity.

In the process of cooperative cross-activity, the leading role is played by a skilled teacher who conducts a master class and uses group forms of interaction with the participants of the workshop and engages them in active creative activity. A skilled teacher analyzes himself and notes the professional difficulties that arise in the activities of the workshop participants. Based on

the results of the work, all participants of the workshop, including the skilled teacher, according to the results of the diagnosis, needs, abilities, and the level of readiness for independent creative activity, create an individual educational path or an individual plan of independent education to overcome professional difficulties they make.[3]

Analysis and results. It is known that the place of the science of literature, which is a powerful weapon in the education of today's young generation, in their development into mature people in all respects, is incomparable. Because the worldview of the student is formed and the character is educated through the artistic work. The young generation will get to know the past of our people and country through books, and will enjoy the priceless heritage left by their great ancestors. A special place is given to the development of independent goals, plans, strategies and criteria of self-evaluation of the problem-based educational technology. Initially, each teacher learns from the experience of a master teacher at the level of samples and benchmarks, tested in practice, described in methodological developments and recommendations, uses two-way communication, reforms his actions according to the results, he works on the basis of a "methodical guide", "template" and the experience of a skilled teacher. In this process, the special pedagogical competence also increases, that is, he has enough information to carry out the pedagogical activity at the necessary level.

After that, the teacher turns to the work of innovation: to find for himself the changing non-standard ways of solving pedagogical problems by a pedagogue, or to create and find original approaches for himself and others, individual methods that restore a certain pedagogical experience taste.

The fact that the problem is new requires the use of new methods of solving it, such as jump-like work, heuristics, introduction of search patterns, a large role of semantics, meaningful analysis of the problem. In this process, along with verbal-logical, well-understood generalizations, intuitive practical generalizations that initially do not find their proper reflection in words are very important. They appear in the process of analyzing demonstrative situations, solving concrete practical problems, analyzing real actions with objects or their models. This makes it easier to search for the unknown, but this search process is carried out intuitively, outside the clear field of consciousness. At the first stage, there is a creative attitude to knowledge, and a chaotic independent satisfaction of the creative need for knowledge, which appears in the absence of the mastered independent educational technology, based on the situation.

Conclusions and suggestions. As a result of improving the creative activity of future elementary school teachers, there will be an increase in their other activities as well. It should be said that the improvement of scientific and creative activity is a gradual and continuous process. If it starts in a higher education institution, it continues in the workplace. Each higher education teacher can choose any heuristic forms and methods of teaching students when forming an individual style of pedagogical activity. At the same time, the results of their application should ensure a positive impact on the development of professional competences of future primary school teachers based on creative approaches.

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